

METHODOLOGICAL ASPECT OF TEACHING COMMUNICATION

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with peculiarities of developing communicative competence in teaching secondary school pupils. More attention is paid to practical aspect of this matter

The technology of **communicative language teaching** is based on using of various methodical techniques of practice situations of real interaction and the organization of pupils group activity (in steams, in small groups) for the purpose of the joint decision of communicative problems.

In its purest form, a communicative activity is an activity in which there is:

- a desire to communicate
- a communicative purpose
- a focus on language content not language forms

- a variety of language used
- no teacher intervention

- no control or simplification of the material [23; 95].

Let's examine each characteristic in turn.

1. A desire to communicate. In a communicative activity there must be a reason to communicate. When someone asks a question, the person must wish to get some information or some other form of result. There must be either an 'information gap' or an 'opinion gap' or some other reason to communicate.

2. A communicative purpose. When we ask students to describe their bedroom furniture to their partners, we are creating an artificial 'communicative purpose' and

making the activity more artificial by asking them to do it in English. We also create artificial 'information gaps' by giving different information to pairs of students so that they can have a reason to exchange information.

3. A focus on language content not language forms. In real life, we do not ask about our friend's family in order to practice 'have got' forms. We ask the question because we are interested in the information. That is to say, we are interested in the language content and not in the language forms.

4. A variety of language is used. In normal communication, we do not repeatedly use the same language forms. In fact, we usually try to avoid repetition. In many classroom activities we often try to create situations in which students will repeatedly use a limited number of language patterns. This is also artificial.

5. No teacher intervention. When you are buying a ticket for The Lion King at the theatre, your teacher is not usually beside you to 'help' or 'correct' your English. Teacher intervention in classroom communicative activities adds to the artificiality.

6. No control or simplification of the material. In the classroom, we often use graded or simplified materials as prompts

for communicative activities. These will not be available in the real world.

The main activity form in which communication is realized presents in the group work.

The goals of group work. The following description of the goals of group work focuses on the spoken use of language. There are several reasons for this focus. Firstly, group work is most commonly used to get learners talking to each other. Secondly, much research on group work in language learning has studied spoken activity, partly because this is the most easily observed and recorded. Thirdly, most teachers use speaking activities in unprincipled ways.

How such activities can be used and adapted to achieve goals in language-learning classes? Group work can help learning in the following ways.

1. Negotiation of input: Group work provides an opportunity for learners to get exposure to language that they can understand (negotiate comprehensible input) and which contains unknown items for them to learn. There has been considerable research on the possible sources of this input and the processes of negotiation, with the general recommendation that group work properly handled is one of the most valuable sources.

2. New language items: Group work gives learners exposure to a range of language items and language functions. This will often require pre-teaching of the needed language items. Group work provides more opportunities for use of the new items compared to the opportunities in teacher-led classes. Group work may also improve the quality of these opportunities in terms of individualization, motivation, depth of processing, and affective climate.

3. Fluency: Group work allows learners to develop fluency in the use of language features that they have already learned. The arguments supporting group

The superior-inferior arrangement in group work is a parallel to traditional class teaching. The essential feature of the arrangement is that one or more learners have all the information that the others in the group need. Here are two examples.

One learner has a complete text. The other learners have some important words from the text. By asking yes/no questions using those words as clues, the learners try to reconstruct the text.

One learner has a dictation text that she dictates to the others in the group. They write the dictation.

The best seating arrangement of the members of the group is with the person in the superior position facing the others. All the others should be an equal distance from

the person with the information. Notice that this arrangement has parallels with the combining arrangement. The combining arrangement may be viewed as a set of superior-inferior arrangements with every learner in the group having the chance to be in the superior position—that is, having information that others need and do not have.

The social relationship amongst the members of a superior-inferior group is one of inequality. The person with the information is in a superior position. This person may gain status from being in this position or may need to be a person with such status.

Research on peer teaching with native speakers shows that the superior-inferior arrangement can result in a lot of useful learning, particularly in pair work.

The most suitable tasks for superior-inferior group work include:

1. data gathering, e. g., interviews, questioning;
2. providing directions, e. g., telling how to get to a place on the map, providing instructions about how to arrange parts to make a complete item;
3. completion.

The individual arrangement of the group-work means that each learner has the same information but must perform individually with a part of that information.

The Say It! Exercise is a good example of this:

All the learners in a group can see a grid:

	1	2	3
A	What animals are helped by the tree?	What animals help the tree?	What animals hurt the tree?
B	Name five parts of a tree.	Explain why the tree is like a small world.	Explain what a twig is.
C	What is your favorite part of a tree? Why?	What is the biggest tree near us? Near your home?	How do trees help?

Each section of the grid has a different task. The learners take turns to name a section of the grid, e. g., B 1, and the next learner in the group has to carry out the task. The exercise is based on an article called "The World of a Tree". The learners would read it before doing the exercise.

Unlike the superior-inferior arrangement and combining arrangement, no learner has information that the others do not have. Unlike the cooperating arrangement, each learner makes an individual performance which is not necessarily helped by the others in the group. The major effects of the individual arrangement are to increase the time each learner can spend on a task, and to ensure that each learner participates.

The learners in the group need to have equal access to the material and be in sight of each other. Sitting in a circle is usually the most convenient.

The most suitable tasks for the individual arrangement in group work include:

1. solving problems, e. g., role play activities where each individual must perform in a certain way;

2. repetition, e. g., a chain story where learners retell the story to each other and see the changes that occur in retelling;

3. completion, e. g., each learner has to add a part to complete a story.

Group work like any other class activity, can quickly become a routine. Once students are used to it and have regular working partners, it can be organized quickly and easily (by saying "Now get into your groups"). The first new times that teachers try to make group work are very important - they need to give more careful instructions and know exactly how they will divide the class.

Language teaching practices were developed in organizing class into groups.

Thus, we can state that types of group work are: formal learning groups, informal learning groups, study teams.

Types of group work arrangement are: the cooperating arrangement, the superior-interior arrangement, the combining arrangement and the individual arrangement.

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